

Frequency of Transfusion-Transmitted Infections and Associated Factors in Children With β -Thalassemia Receiving Regular Blood Transfusions

Dr. Rida Batool (Corresponding Author)

Women Medical Officer , THQ Hospital Chichawatni, Sahiwal

Email: ridabatool920@gmail.com

Dr. Faisal Saleem

Medical officer , Nancy Fullwood Hospital Society, Christian Hospital, Sahiwal

Dr. Farzeen Javaid

Women Medical Officer, Usman Hospital, Sahiwal

Abstract

Background: β -thalassemia is a hereditary hemoglobin disorder that often requires lifelong blood transfusions, placing affected children at increased risk of transfusion-transmitted infections. **Objective:** To determine the frequency of transfusion-transmitted infections and associated factors among children with β -thalassemia receiving regular blood transfusions. **Methods:** This cross-sectional study included 100 children diagnosed with β -thalassemia. Demographic data, clinical findings, and transfusion history were recorded. Blood samples were screened for hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C virus, and human immunodeficiency virus using standard serological methods. **Results:** The study included 100 children with β -thalassemia (mean age 7.07 ± 3.05 years; 56% male). β -thalassemia major was present in 95% of patients. Clinically, 49% had hepatosplenomegaly with pallor and jaundice. Overall, 38% had transfusion-transmitted infections, with hepatitis B virus (28%) being the most common, followed by hepatitis C virus (8%) and HIV (2%). Infection rates were significantly higher in children weighing >20 kg (57.9% vs. 25.8%, $p = 0.001$) and in those with a disease duration of 7–12 years (57.6% vs. 28.4%, $p = 0.005$). No significant association was observed between infection status and type of β -thalassemia ($p = 0.52$). **Conclusion:** It is concluded that transfusion-transmitted infections are common among children with β -thalassemia, with hepatitis B virus being the most frequently identified infection. Increased infection risk is associated with longer disease duration and higher body weight, reflecting cumulative transfusion exposure, while the type of β -thalassemia shows no significant association.

Author Details

Keywords: B-Thalassemia; Transfusion-Transmitted Infections; Hepatitis B Virus; Hepatitis C Virus; Blood Transfusion; Pediatric Patients

Received on 10 Apr 2025

Accepted on 05 Jun 2025

Published on 30 Jun 2025

Corresponding E-mail & Author*:

Dr Rida Batool*

Women Medical Officer, THQ Hospital, Chichawatni, Sahiwal
Email: ridabatool920@gmail.com

Introduction

β -thalassemia major is one of the most common inherited hemoglobinopathies worldwide and represents a major public health burden in low- and middle-income countries, particularly in South Asia [1]. It is an autosomal recessive disorder caused by mutations in the β -globin gene, resulting in reduced or absent synthesis of β -globin chains and subsequent ineffective erythropoiesis, chronic hemolytic anemia, and marrow expansion [2]. Children affected with β -thalassemia major typically present within the first two years of life and require lifelong regular blood transfusions to sustain adequate hemoglobin levels and normal growth [3]. Pakistan bears a disproportionately high burden of β -thalassemia, with an estimated carrier frequency of 5–7% and more than 100,000 transfusion-dependent patients currently living with the disease [4]. Each year, approximately 5,000–9,000 children are born with β -thalassemia major in the country, largely due to consanguineous marriages and the absence of a nationwide prenatal screening program [5]. Despite advances in disease management, regular blood transfusion remains the cornerstone of therapy, placing affected children at persistent risk for transfusion-related complications [6]. One of the most serious complications of repeated blood transfusions is the acquisition of transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs), particularly hepatitis B virus (HBV), hepatitis C virus (HCV), and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) [7]. Frequent exposure to donor blood, coupled with inadequate screening practices, significantly increases the vulnerability of thalassemia patients to these infections compared with the general pediatric population [8]. The presence of TTIs further complicates clinical management by accelerating liver disease, impairing iron chelation therapy, increasing morbidity, and adversely affecting long-term survival and quality of life [9]. Several studies from Pakistan and neighboring regions have reported alarmingly high rates of TTIs among multi-transfused β -thalassemia patients. Reported prevalence of TTIs ranges from 25% to over 35%, with HCV being the most commonly detected infection, followed by HBV and HIV [10–12]. A meta-analysis of regional studies demonstrated pooled seroprevalence estimates of approximately 26% for HCV and 3% for HBV, highlighting substantial gaps in transfusion safety systems [1]. These findings underscore the persistent failure to ensure uniform donor screening, reliance on replacement or paid donors, and limited access to advanced screening techniques such as nucleic acid testing in many blood banks [13].

Objective

To determine the frequency of transfusion-transmitted infections and associated risk factors among children with β -thalassemia receiving regular blood transfusions.

Methodology

This was a cross-sectional observational study conducted at the Department of Pediatric Medicine, Sahiwal Teaching Hospital, Sahiwal, from 9 December 2023 to 8 June 2024. The study included 100 children aged 1–16 years diagnosed with β -thalassemia and receiving regular blood transfusions.

Inclusion Criteria

Children aged 1–16 years of either gender

Diagnosed cases of β -thalassemia major confirmed on hemoglobin electrophoresis

Receiving regular blood transfusions for more than three months

Exclusion Criteria

Children with documented chronic hepatitis B, hepatitis C, or HIV infection or those receiving treatment for these infections during the last three months

Children born to HBV- or HCV-positive mothers
 Children with other hemoglobinopathies such as sickle cell anemia, HbS/ β -thalassemia, or HbC/ β -thalassemia

Data Collection

After obtaining approval from the institutional ethical committee, eligible patients admitted to the pediatric ward were enrolled using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. Written informed consent was obtained from parents or legal guardians. Demographic and clinical data including age, gender, body weight, type of β -thalassemia, duration of disease, and frequency of blood transfusions were recorded on a structured proforma. A 5 mL venous blood sample was collected under aseptic conditions and sent to the hospital laboratory for screening of hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C virus, and human immunodeficiency virus using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Presence of any of these infections was labeled as transfusion-transmitted infection according to operational definitions. Patients found positive were managed according to standard hospital protocols.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0. Quantitative variables such as age, body weight, duration of thalassemia, and frequency of blood transfusions were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Categorical variables including gender, type of thalassemia, and transfusion-transmitted infections were presented as frequencies and percentages. Stratification was performed for age, gender, body weight, duration of thalassemia, and type of thalassemia. Associations between transfusion-transmitted infections and stratified variables were assessed using the chi-square test. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The mean age of the study population was **7.07 \pm 3.05 years**, with a slight male predominance (**56% males, 44% females**). Most patients had **β -thalassemia major (95%)**, while **3%** had intermedia and **2%** had minor disease. Clinically, the most frequent presentation was **hepatosplenomegaly with pallor and jaundice**, observed in **49%** of patients, followed by **hepatosplenomegaly with pallor (23%)**, **pallor alone (16%)**, **splenomegaly with pallor (11%)**, and isolated hepatosplenomegaly (**1%**). Regarding transfusion-transmitted infections, **38%** of patients were infected, while **62%** were infection-free. **Hepatitis B virus** was the most common infection (**28%**), followed by **hepatitis C virus (8%)** and **HIV (2%)**, highlighting a substantial infectious burden in this transfusion-dependent population.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic Characteristics, Disease Profile, Clinical Findings, and Transfusion-Transmitted Infection Pattern (N = 100)

Domain	Variable	Category / Description	n	SD/%
Demographics	Age (years)	Mean \pm SD	—	7.07 \pm 3.05
	Gender	Male	56	56.0
		Female	44	44.0
Disease Characteristics	Type of β -thalassemia	Major	95	95.0
		Intermedia	3	3.0
		Minor	2	2.0
Clinical Findings	Physical	Hepatosplenomegaly	1	1.0

	examination	only		
		Hepatosplenomegaly + pallor	23	23.0
		Hepatosplenomegaly + pallor + jaundice	49	49.0
		Pallor only	16	16.0
		Splenomegaly + pallor	11	11.0
Transfusion-Transmitted Infections	Overall TTI status	TTI positive	38	38.0
		TTI negative	62	62.0
	Type of infection	Hepatitis B virus (HBV)	28	28.0
		Hepatitis C virus (HCV)	8	8.0
		Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV)	2	2.0

Children weighing **more than 20 kg** showed a markedly higher infection rate (**57.9%**) compared to those weighing **8–20 kg** (**25.8%**), with a statistically significant association (**p = 0.001**). Similarly, patients with a longer disease duration of **7–12 years** had a significantly higher infection rate (**57.6%**) than those with **1–6 years** of disease (**28.4%**, **p = 0.005**). When stratified by thalassemia type, **38.9%** of patients with β -thalassemia major were infection positive, compared to **33.3%** in intermedia and **0%** in minor cases; however, this association was not statistically significant (**p = 0.52**). Overall, **38%** of the cohort was infection positive and **62%** infection negative, indicating that infection risk is primarily related to cumulative transfusion exposure rather than disease subtype.

Table 2: Association of Transfusion-Transmitted Infections with Clinical and Disease-Related Variables (N = 100)

Variable	Category	TTI Positive n (%)	TTI Negative n (%)	Total n (%)	p-value
Body Weight (kg)	8–20	16 (25.8)	46 (74.2)	62 (100)	
	>20	22 (57.9)	16 (42.1)	38 (100)	0.001
Duration of Thalassemia (years)	1–6	19 (28.4)	48 (71.6)	67 (100)	
	7–12	19 (57.6)	14 (42.4)	33 (100)	0.005
Type of β-thalassemia	Major	37 (38.9)	58 (61.1)	95 (100)	
	Intermedia	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)	3 (100)	
	Minor	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)	2 (100)	0.52
Overall	—	38 (38.0)	62 (62.0)	100 (100)	—

Figure 1. Prevalence of Transfusion-Transmitted Infections by Clinical and Disease-Related Variables

Discussion

This study demonstrates a substantial burden of transfusion-transmitted infections among children with β -thalassemia, with more than one-third of patients (38%) affected. This finding underscores the persistent vulnerability of transfusion-dependent pediatric populations despite routine donor screening. A similar magnitude of infection burden has been reported in previous research, indicating that transfusion-related infections remain a major challenge in resource-limited settings [14]. Hepatitis B virus was the most frequently identified infection (28%), followed by hepatitis C virus (8%) and HIV (2%). The predominance of hepatitis viruses mirrors patterns reported in previous research and may reflect gaps in vaccination coverage, window-period transmission, or inconsistencies in blood screening practices. These infections contribute significantly to long-term morbidity in thalassemia patients, complicating clinical management and worsening prognosis [15]. The study further highlights the role of cumulative transfusion exposure in infection risk. Children with a longer disease duration (7–12 years) had a significantly higher infection rate (57.6%) compared to those with a shorter duration (28.4%), and children weighing more than 20 kg also showed a markedly higher prevalence of infections (57.9%). Previous research has similarly demonstrated that prolonged survival and repeated transfusions increase the likelihood of acquiring transfusion-transmitted infections, supporting the cumulative exposure hypothesis [16].

Clinical findings reflected advanced disease severity, with nearly half of the patients presenting with hepatosplenomegaly, pallor, and jaundice. Such manifestations have been linked in previous research to chronic hemolysis and prolonged transfusion dependence, conditions that further increase susceptibility to transfusion-related infections [17, 18]. Importantly, no significant association was observed between the type of β -thalassemia and infection status, reinforcing that transfusion exposure rather than disease subtype is the primary determinant of infection risk. Overall, these findings are consistent with previous research and emphasize the need for

strengthened blood safety measures. Improved donor screening, strict regulatory oversight, and effective hepatitis B immunization programs are essential to reduce preventable infectious complications in transfusion-dependent thalassemia patients.

Conclusion

It is concluded that transfusion-transmitted infections represent a significant and preventable complication among children with β -thalassemia receiving regular blood transfusions. More than one-third of patients were affected, with hepatitis B virus emerging as the predominant infection. Longer disease duration and higher body weight were significantly associated with infection, indicating that cumulative transfusion exposure is the principal risk factor rather than thalassemia subtype. These findings emphasize the need for strengthened blood screening practices, strict regulatory oversight, and effective preventive strategies to reduce infection-related morbidity in transfusion-dependent thalassemia patients.

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